

First MARVIC Market End-User Forum Public Summary Report

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Introduction

The Market End-User Forum, led by **Agrosolutions**, aims to capture information from players of carbon markets (corporations committing to net-zero claims, certifiers of carbon credits, companies developing CFS, agricultural advisors) to ensure that MARVIC project outcomes are user-centred and capable of being upscaled. The primary goal is to build trust around Carbon Farming and develop key messages that support the implementation of Monitoring, Reporting, and Verification (MRV) systems.

This report aims to provide a first insight into the activities of this Forum, which are still ongoing. By the end of the project in 2027, the outcomes from this and other Forums (Policy and Climate Advocacy) will inform a major policy brief and a post-project implementation plan.

Methodology

The forum consisted of **2 webinars and a cycle of 10 bilateral interviews**.

The first webinar focused on general presentation of the MARVIC Project and the Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming (CRCF) Regulation. It brought together 167 participants, representing a wide range of European actors, future users of the CRCF (so called “end-users”): Project developers, farmers or farmers' representatives, agricultural cooperatives, companies in the agri-food sector, etc., as well as researchers and students. The webinar featured presentations by three speakers: Edouard Lanckriet (Agrosolutions), Greet Ruyschaert (ILVO), and Valeria Forlin (DG CLIMA).

The webinar included the definition of a set of questions to be asked to participants during the webinar via an online Klaxoon form, in order to identify who they are, their level of knowledge of the CRCF, their expectations for the webinar, and their views on a series of proposals for the CRCF (see the “results” section for the questions asked).

Bilateral interviews (45 minutes each) were conducted after the 1st webinar; their objective was to provide in-depth feedback on the first webinar and highlight expectations regarding the topics to be addressed in the second webinar. The interviews consisted of two parts: 1. Answers to the interviewee’s questions on the CRCF; 2. Open questions asked by Agrosolutions on key aspects of the CRCF.

The second webinar focused on methodology issues to bridge Scope 3 reporting and carbon credits MRV. The second webinar gathered 258 participants, mostly of the same categories than for the first webinar, but with a more international profile. In line with the requests expressed by interviewees, the webinar focused on the link between Scope 3 reporting and MRV of carbon credits. It was designed as a roundtable with invited experts. Eight experts took part in the roundtable: Valeria Forlin (DG CLIMA), Jan Peter Lesschen (CAFAMORE project), Kim Schoppink (SBTi), Matt Ramlow (GHG Protocol), Ichsani Wheeler and Kelly Ann Ross (OGCR project), Marion Verles (SustainCERT), and Naomi Montenegro Navarro (Value Change Initiative).

For both webinars, participants had **very heterogeneous** degrees of knowledge of the mechanisms of the CRCF, and more generally of carbon farming MRV schemes, as well as of international standards or environmental footprint measurement schemes.

The webinars and bilateral interviews offered to end users were highly appreciated by participants. The presence of speakers recognised as experts in their fields, and in particular the contributions of Valeria Forlin in helping to disseminate information on the CRCF, were especially valued. The questions raised during the webinars and interviews made it possible to identify and highlight a series of key issues for end users.

Key Results

The events carried out by the Forum were instrumental in disseminating the MARVIC project and its role within the CRCF, as well as understanding the needs and expectations of end users. In addition, a series of key points featured in the feedback on the EU Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming (CRCF) Regulation during both the Q&A sessions of the webinars and through the bilateral interviews is provided below

A. Methodological Aspects

A strong consensus (83% of respondents) supports the use of open-source approaches for model validation and calibration, comparison of quantification methods, and verification of carbon credits. Beyond transparency and robustness, open-source solutions are viewed as a way to reduce costs if deployed centrally, and to facilitate access to primary data and harmonization between public and private datasets.

Regarding data quality, 57% consider the use of generic or simplified primary data acceptable during the initial ramp-up phase, provided that more specific data are progressively introduced.

There is no consensus between reliance on Tier 3 models and physical soil measurements. Agri-food companies favour Tier 3 models to avoid the cost and uncertainty of soil sampling, while project developers stress the need for measurement-remeasurement approaches until models are fully calibrated. All stakeholders agree on the need for harmonised guidelines for soil sampling (depth, frequency, protocols).

Finally, current CRCF methodological guidance is perceived as uneven, with a lack of operational consistency and field-level applicability.

B. Governance and Policy Alignment

Stakeholders underline the need for coherence between the CRCF and EU policies on climate, soils, bioenergy, and biodiversity. This alignment is seen as essential to ensure consistency across emerging environmental credit schemes and to secure the economic viability of farm transition models.

Uncertainty remains regarding the operational functioning of the CRCF, notably the validation of certification frameworks: scope, timelines, responsibilities, duration of approval, revision processes, and risks for projects if a framework loses CRCF recognition.

Project developers also stress the importance of adequately sizing validation, auditing, and verification bodies to avoid future bottlenecks.

C. Interaction with Scope 3 and Carbon Markets

Clear rules are urgently needed to align CRCF credits with corporate Scope 3 reporting. Competition between carbon credit schemes and emission-factor-based grain premium programs creates confusion and limits scalability, mainly due to unclear rules on double counting and claims (offset, inset, contribution, non-permanence). While 80% oppose double counting between CRCF credits and Scope 3 reporting, 20% support conditional allowances.

D. Centralised Registry

A centralised EU registry is widely viewed (77%) as a key operational tool to manage MRV, Scope 3 reporting, and double counting. Most respondents (80%) also support its use for “supply-shed” Scope 3 accounting. Opinions differ on whether reporting obligations should apply at farm level (42%) or company level (58%).

Attention points include transparency of calculations and claims, management of changing plot boundaries, alignment of baselines with crop rotations, and mechanisms to address leakage risks.

E. Economic Value and Market Structuring

The CRCF is perceived as a major opportunity to structure a credible and scalable agricultural carbon market, with significantly higher remuneration for farmers than current voluntary markets. However, major uncertainties remain about demand drivers, the nature of claims associated with CRCF units, and how value will be maintained across heterogeneous methods and pedoclimatic contexts.

Stakeholders also call for a centralised, cross-environmental credit architecture (carbon, biodiversity, water, nature) to maximise market value and coherence.

Finally, regulatory flexibility is considered crucial: payment schemes must allow advance or regular payments to farmers to enable upfront investment in the low-carbon transition.